

Lecane papuana no

Lecane pyriformis no

Lecane unguita no

Brachionus patalus 0.16mg T/0.75x10⁶ Chlorella

Brachionus patalus 0.0mg T/1.5x10⁶ Chlorella

Brachionus patalus 0.16mg T/1.5x10⁶ Chlorella

Brachionus patalus 0.31mg T/1.5x10⁶ Chlorella

Brachionus patalus 0.0mg T/3.0x10⁶ Chlorella

Brachionus patalus 0.16mg T/3.0x10⁶ Chlorella

Brachionus patalus 0.31mg T/3.0x10⁶ Chlorella

Brachionus patalus 0.0mg T/6.0x10⁶ Chlorella

Brachionus patalus 0.31mg T/6.0x10⁶ Chlorella

Brachionus plicatilis no

Brachinous rotundiforus 0ml L-carnitine

Brachinous rotundiforus 1ml L-carnitine

Brachinous rotundiforus 10ml L-carnitine

Brachinous rotundiforus 100ml L-carnitine

Brachinous rotundiforus 1000ml L-carnitine

Brachionus calyciflorus Control – Chlorella

Brachionus patalus Control – Chlorella

Brachionus patalus Partially treated wastewater

Brachionus rubens Control – Chlorella

Brachionus rubens Treated wastewater

Brachionus rubens Crude wastewater

Anuraeopsis fissa 0g NaCl

Anuraeopsis fissa 0.375g NaCl

Anuraeopsis fissa 0.75g NaCl

Anuraeopsis fissa 1.5g Na Cl

Brachionus calyciflorus 0g NaCl

Brachionus havanaensis 0g NaCl

Brachionus havanaensis 0.375g NaCl

Brachionus havanaensis 0.75g NaCl

Brachionus havanaensis 1.5g NaCl

Brachionus patalus 0.75g NaCl

Brachionus patalus 1.5g NaCl

Brachionus patalus 3.0g NaCl

Brachionus rubens 0g NaCl

Brachionus rubens 0.75g NaCl

Brachionus rubens 1.5g NaCl

Brachionus rubens 3.0g NaCl

Brachionus rubens 4.5g NaCl

Brachionus calyciflorus CV(1×10^6)+P(1.1×10^5)

Brachionus calyciflorus CV(1×10^6)+P(2.1×10^5)

Brachionus calyciflorus CV(1×10^6)+P(2.1×10^6)

Brachionus calyciflorus CV(1x10⁶)

Brachionus calyciflorus CV(1×10^6)+P(8.6×10^6)

